

FEATURES OF LONG-DISTANCE HF RADIO PROPAGATION: RESULTS OF 15 YEARS OF DOPPLER OBSERVATIONS FROM ANTARCTICA

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HF radio waves are an effective tool for remote sensing of the Earth's ionosphere, as ionospheric plasma frequencies fall within the HF range. It means that the radio signals of this range interact most effectively with the ionospheric plasma. The primary instruments traditionally used for sensing the ionosphere are radars for vertical sounding or ionosondes operating in the HF range. Additionally, the Super-DARN – network of coherent radars operates in the same range aimed at retrieval the parameters of plasma convection in Polar regions and electric fields leading to convection.

Over the last 50 years, the Institute of Radio Astronomy of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine has been developing a method of HF Doppler diagnostics of the ionosphere using narrowband radiation from existing transmitters as probing signals. The most suitable signals for these purposes are those from time service stations, as they closely adhere to frequency and time standards.

The first experiments on HF Doppler sounding of the ionosphere conducted both at the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station (UAS) and aboard a research vessel took place during the 2001–2002 seasonal expedition. Since 2010, continuous HF Doppler monitoring of the ionosphere over long-distance radio paths has been performed at UAS using the signals transmitted by time service stations in the Northern Hemisphere. 15 years of almost non-stop measurements of signals from the RWM (Europe) and CHU (North America) radio stations allowed to experimentally detect and describe 4 stable mechanisms of radio wave propagation over super-long distances. The recent deployment of a mobile radio observatory aboard the research vessel *Noosfera* enabled the testing of several hypotheses concerning long-distance HF propagation mechanisms. Furthermore, we have developed a model describing variations in intensity and Doppler frequency shift of the signals over long-distant radio paths. The model uses the variation in the integral illumination of the path as its principal parameter.

In this presentation, we will demonstrate the results of long-term observations of the features of long-distance propagation of HF radio signals toward the Antarctic Peninsula. We will compare experimental measurements of signal parameters with those predicted by the model, discuss the causes of observed discrepancies, and explore future prospects for HF radio sounding of the ionosphere over ultra-long-distance radio paths.